

Determinants of Customer Satisfaction at Fast Food Restaurants Located in Kishoreganj District of Bangladesh

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Abstract

To explore the determinants of customer satisfaction at Kishoreganj based fast-food restaurants in Bangladesh is the core objective of this research. The research design is descriptive and quantitative in nature where data was collected from 280 (sample size) frequent fast food experiencing customers comprising of students, job holders and others residing in Kishoreganj districts of Bangladesh, applying nonprobability convenience sampling technique through structured online survey questionnaire consisting of demographic data namely age, gender, occupation and income etc. and determinants of consumer satisfaction on five point Likert rating ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Collected data was analyzed through multiple linear regressions by using statistical software SPSS version 20. Research findings show that at $P < 0.05$, four independent variables like price fairness ($\beta = 0.213$), ambience ($\beta = 0.344$), service quality ($\beta = 0.224$), food quality ($\beta = 0.231$), etc. are positively associated with dependent variable like customer satisfaction while one independent variable namely restaurant location ($\beta = -0.172$), is negatively associated with customer satisfaction. Hence, H1 to H4 except H5 was supported. The paper also found that, among all the determinants, ambience with highest $\beta = 0.344$ was the most influential determinant of customer satisfaction. Therefore, the research contributes to existing body of knowledge related to customer satisfaction at restaurant industry by highlighting the priority of selected determinants. Furthermore, it provides guidelines and suggestions for fast food restaurants to enhance customer satisfaction.

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Introduction

Fast food restaurants are one of the fastest growing food segments worldwide (Goyal & Singh, 2009). The increased number of people spending money on fast food made it more available to them, indicating significant changes in their regular consumption habits (Gabrow, 2021). Fast food has become preferred choice among Bangladeshi due to packed schedule of work routine, lifestyle, and demanding family (Habib, 2011). Customer satisfaction is considered as important element for success in restaurant sector (Namin, 2017). Malik et al., (2012) are of the opinion that price fairness is still one of the important rules to create customer satisfaction and purchasing retention. Nowadays, customers put their attention not only on food quality but also other factors like ambience or atmosphere, variety of food and location of restaurants (Annamdevula & Bellamkonda, 2016). Recent studies highlighted the importance of food quality (Lefrid, 2021; Singh et al., 2021a; Singh et al., 2021b; Slack et al., 2021; Richardson et al., 2019; Uddin, 2019; Namin, 2017), service quality (Gabrow, 2021; Chun & Nyam-Ochir, 2020; Saneva & Chortoseva, 2020; Uslu & Eren, 2020; Zhong & Moon, 2020; Sahak et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2017), ambience (Hutchinson & Parsa, 2014; Horng et al., 2015; Sester et al., 2013; Njite, 2015; Chiguvu & Douglas, 2017;) Restaurant location (Dhisasmito & Kumar, 2020; Hassan et al., 2013; Lewis & Shoemaker, 1997) and price fairness (Javed et al., 2021; Saxena & Taneja, 2020; McNeil & Young, 2019) on customer satisfaction. Putro et al. (2014) defined service quality as an endeavor to meet consumers' requirements and aspirations, as well as the accuracy of delivery in the context of consumer expectations. Following that, customer service quality ratings are created based on a comparison of expectations and actuality of the services received (Japrianto, 2007; Lu, et al, 2015). Customer satisfaction is increased through the improvement of product quality (Jahanshahi et al., 2011). Factors namely ambience or atmosphere, variety of food, food quality, service quality, price fairness, and location of restaurants are taken into consideration as the important predictors, hence, examining these factors are assumed vital in analysing customer satisfaction. However, the inconsistent findings from prior studies require an exploration to further support the evidence. Therefore, researcher conducted this first empirical research to investigate the predictors like price fairness, ambience, service quality, food quality, restaurant location etc. of customer satisfaction at restaurant sector in the context of Kishoreganj, Bangladesh.

Research Objectives

The major objective of the research is to examine the predictors of customer satisfaction in restaurant sector in the context of kishoreganj, Bangladesh. Other objectives mentioned below are also be analyzed to derive valuable insight regarding customer satisfaction at restaurant sector. (a) To explore the determinants likely price fairness, ambience, service quality, food quality, restaurant location etc. of customer satisfaction at restaurants located in Kishoreganj, Bangladesh. (b) To assess the relationship between price fairness, ambience, service quality, food quality, restaurant location etc. determinants and customer satisfaction at restaurants located in Kishoreganj, Bangladesh. (c) To evaluate the impacts of price fairness, ambience, service quality, food quality, restaurant location etc. determinants on customer satisfaction at restaurants located in Kishoreganj, Bangladesh. & (d) To investigate the best determinants of customer satisfaction at restaurants located in Kishoreganj, Bangladesh.

Literature Review

Because of the importance of customer satisfaction and retention in the food industry, multiple studies have been undertaken to look into the impact of various aspects on customer satisfaction and retention. While some of the research focused on food quality, others looked

at other consumer characteristics and circumstance elements in relation to customer happiness and retention (Mannan et al., 2019).

Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction refers to how well a product or service meets or exceeds a customer's expectations (Homburg & Stock, 2004). Consumer satisfaction is defined as a customer's assessment of services and goods that provide favorable outcomes (Ali, 2015). According to Rahim et al. (2015), in order to achieve a high level of consumer happiness, service providers must deliver a high level of service quality, since service quality is seen as the cornerstone of consumer contentment. In his study, Oliver (1981) focused on customer satisfaction, characterizing it as a psychological, constructive, and personal appraisal of a client's purchasing behavior. Customer satisfaction is a driving factor for businesses to maintain their competitive edge, and it has a big influence on repeat customers, word of mouth, and consumer loyalty (Zhang et al., 2013). Customer satisfaction is the act of going above and beyond to meet a customer's requests, wants, or requirements. Customer satisfaction is defined as satisfying the expectations of customers in terms of satisfaction-related factors (Malik, 2012). Previous research has shown that in order to achieve customer happiness, the products and services offered must be of high quality (Padma & Astuti, 2016). As a result, products and services can be gratifying when they provide what consumers want and need, and the company's performance meets the customers' expectations (Santouridis & Trivellas, 2010).

Price Fairness and Customer Satisfaction

In his study, Bolton (2013) stated that "customers must pay for a benefit," which he refers to as pricing fairness. "What the consumer paid for the product or services" is how price is defined (Zeithaml, 1988). One of the most important factors that influences consumer satisfaction and behavior intentions is price (Andaleeb et al., 2006). The management must choose a value that takes into account customer perceptions as well as their capacity to pay (Shahzadi et al, 2018). According to Koseoglu (2016), pricing fairness has a major impact on consumer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction and retention are tied to prices that are a realistic reflection of service quality (Hanaysha, 2016). Fairly charged prices that are reflected in service and product quality are seen to be a contributing element in customer satisfaction and retention (Andaleeb & Conway, 2006; Kaura et al., 2015). Customer happiness is influenced by a number of factors, one of which is pricing (Saxena & Taneja, 2020). According to Uddin (2019), pricing is a predictor of consumer happiness. Price has a considerable beneficial effect on consumer happiness, according to a new research conducted at fast food businesses (Singh et al., 2021b; McNeil et al., 2019). Furthermore, while purchasing fast food, pricing or value for money has a favorable impact on consumer satisfaction (Slack et al., 2020; Zhong & Moon, 2020). When clients believe the price is reasonable and acceptable, they are more likely to be satisfied (Ryu & Han, 2010). In light of previous researches, it is possible to hypothesize that:

H1: *In the fast-food restaurants of Kishoreganj, Bangladesh, Price fairness is absolutely related with customer satisfaction*

Ambience and Customer Satisfaction

In his study, Bitner (1990) argued that restaurants must place a high value on their environment in order to attract more customers and establish customer loyalty. Environment, decor, music, restaurant designs, interior design, and dine-in setting all play a role in determining a restaurant's overall mood, as does staff conduct (Hutchinson & Parsa, 2014). According to Horng et al. (2015), in addition to food quality, restaurant cleanliness has an impact on restaurant efficiency. In their study, Sester et al. (2013) stressed the relevance of a

restaurant's entire ambience. An outstanding ambience tends to enhance client consumption and readiness to return frequently and pay high prices (Njite, 2015). Visitors to a restaurant might witness unique and exceptional experiences that they may not be able to get anywhere else (Chiguvi & Douglas, 2017). This phrase was described by Kotler (1973) in his study as an "attempt to construct a purchasing environment that might elicit particular emotional responses among customers in order to boost purchase potential." It can be assumed, based on past researches, that:

H2: *In the fast-food restaurants of Kishoreganj, Bangladesh, the Ambience is positively related to customer satisfaction.*

Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction

Service quality, according to Zeithaml (1988), is "a customer's assessment of a product's total excellence or superiority." Oliver (1999) defined service quality as the gap between a customer's expectation and their impression of service quality. Customer expectations are formed based on customer perceptions of a service, which serve as benchmarks by which service performance is measured (Ronald, 2006). Relationship quality, which encompasses contentment and trust, has been proven to be highly related with service quality in banks and hospitals in previous research (Hsieh, & Hiang 2004). Customer satisfaction is largely determined by service quality (Gotlieb et al., 1994), and it is an important component of the overall success of food service operations (Lefrid, 2021). Chun and Nyam-Ochir (2020) discovered that service quality and customer satisfaction had a favorable link. Similarly, recent studies have found that service quality has a major impact on consumer satisfaction (Saneva & Chortoseva, 2020; Zhong & Moon, 2020). According to Sahak et al. (2019), offering service on time and surpassing client expectations might boost customer satisfaction at fast food businesses. We can propose the following based on the above literatures:

H3: *In the fast-food restaurants of Kishoreganj, Bangladesh, Service quality is positively related to customer satisfaction.*

Food Quality and Customer Satisfaction

Food quality encompasses a number of factors, including nutrition, cleanliness, freshness, quantity, presentation, and the diversity of foods offered by restaurants (Rana et al, 2017). Food quality is a subjective factor that varies from person to person (Chamhuri & Batt, 2015), with numerous linked components such as flavor, food presentation, food temperature, healthy options, and freshness (Chamhuri & Batt, 2015). (Namkung & Jang, 2007). In their study, Grunert et al (1996) categorized food quality into four categories: taste and smell, safety, efficiency, and method. The food quality of a restaurant has a significant influence on the satisfaction, trust, and views of its consumers (Muna & Cheong, 2018). Customer loyalty connected to food quality may be accomplished in this respect by maintaining continual connection with customers as well as consistently improving the quality of their meals and menus (Seo & Sunhee, 2014). To ensure client happiness, fresh and high-quality food is required (Uddin, 2019). Food quality is linked to customer satisfaction and is important in boosting overall satisfaction (Lefrid, 2021). (Namin, 2017). Food quality was revealed to be a key element in customer satisfaction in recent research at fast food restaurants (Lefrid, 2021; Zhong & Moon, 2020; Richardson et al., 2019). The following hypothesis is developed in light of previous researches:

H4: *In the fast-food restaurants of Kishoreganj, Bangladesh, food quality is positively related to customer satisfaction.*

Restaurant Location (RL) and Customer Satisfaction

According to studies, restaurants that are located in prominent locations, have ample parking, and a ventilated and clean physical environment attract consumers and have a good impact on their satisfaction levels (Minai & Lucky, 2011). According to Hanaysha (2016), a restaurant's accessibility and visibility are critical factors in customer satisfaction. Klassen et al. (2005) investigated the scheduling of food services on a university campus. Because students have less time to go outside of the institution, the study found that they choose to buy food from the campus cafe to fulfill their hunger because they prefer a small walking distance for a quick dinner. Customers like to visit restaurants that are conveniently placed, according to Mattila (2001). Furthermore, in a research conducted by Kivela et al. (2000) based on restaurant themes, the author classified the parking space as a convenience. While Lewis & Shoemaker (1997) discovered in their study that restaurant patrons value low walking distances, and that a convenient location is linked to consumer happiness, purchase intent, and ultimately brand loyalty (Dhisasmito & Kumar, 2020). According to Hassan et al. (2013), because urban living places time limits on customers, they want convenience and want to fulfill their hunger with the least amount of effort. The following hypothesis is investigated based on the literatures:

H5: *In the fast-food restaurants of Kishoreganj, Bangladesh, Restaurant location is positively associated with customer satisfaction.*

Conceptual Framework of Research

As mentioned earlier, the research applied five determinants (price fairness, ambience, service quality food quality, and restaurant location) as the determinants of customer satisfaction in fast food restaurants in kishoreganj, Bangladesh. Figure-1 exhibits the conceptual framework of the research, along with the postulated relationships.

Figure-1: Proposed Conceptual Framework of the Research with postulated relationship

Research Gap

There is severe lack in research regarding customer satisfaction at fast food restaurants in Bangladesh, specifically in kishoreganj district where no research associated with it, is still conducted. Several prior researches are conducted on the factors influencing customer

satisfaction at restaurant industry all around the globe (Singh et al., 2021a; 2021; Richardson et al., 2019; Namin, 2017; Gabrow, 2021; Lefrid, 2021; Chun & Nyam-Ochir, 2020; Slack et al., Saneva & Chortoseva, 2020; Uslu & Eren, 2020; Zhong & Moon, 2020; Sahak et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2017; Uddin, 2019; Javed et al., 2021; Saxena & Taneja, 2020; Singh et al., 2021b; McNeil & Young, 2019) but no specific one is in context of kishoreganj, covering five determinants namely price fairness, ambience, service quality, food quality, restaurant location etc. So this research is a noble attempt to explore these influential determinants of customer satisfaction at restaurants located at kishoreganj. Hence, this research investigates an untapped arena of customer satisfaction and recommends important managerial implications to enhance existing scenario of restaurant sector in Kishoreganj. This research would certainly act as a reference point for future researchers who are willing to carry out studies on similar theme.

Methodology of the Research

Research Design

This research is descriptive and quantitative in nature where data have been collected through convenience sampling technique from 280 regular fast food taking customers residing in Kishoreganj district of Bangladesh. Basically, Kishoreganj is considered as study area in this research due to the scarcity of research conducted here regarding the determinants of customer satisfaction at fast food restaurant sector. Although questionnaire was distributed in Google form between November and December 2021 to 350 frequent customers of restaurants located in kishoreganj but responses from 280 customers was complete which is considered as sample size (N=280) of this research.

Instrumentation

The questionnaire comprises of 20 items under 6 variables and four demographic items namely gender, age, income, occupation and relevant items were adapted from prior researches (Zhong & Moon, 2020; Mumtaz & Chaipoopirutana, 2020; Hanaysha, 2016; Tan et al., 2014; Xia et al., 2004; Anderson et al., 1994; Oliver & Swan, 1989). It was measured using a five-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree) to evaluate customers's level of agreement with the items. The price fairness as a first variable consists of 3 items (Xia et al., 2004; Anderson et al., 1994; Hanaysha, 2016), ambience consists of 3 items (Parasuraman et al., 1988) service quality consists of 4 items (Tan et al., 2014), food quality with 3 items (Zhong & Moon, 2020), restaurant location consists of 3 items (Oliver & Swan, 1989) and customer satisfaction consists of 4 items (Hanaysha, 2016).

Data Analysis Tools

Collected data was analyzed by conducting multiple linear regression analysis (for response related data) and frequency distribution table (for demographic data) through statistical software SPSS version 20 and Microsoft Excel. For ensuring reliability and validity of data, reliability test was performed where value of Cronbach Alpha for each construct was above 0.7 which indicates reliability of data.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Analysis

Table 4.1 : Respondent's Demographic Data

Demographic Characteristics		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Male	105	37.5	37.5
	Female	175	62.5	100.0
		280	100.0	
Age (in years)	15-25 years	53	18.9	18.9
	26-35 years	136	48.6	37.9
	36-45 years	53	18.9	86.4
	Above 45 years	38	13.6	100.0
		280	100.0	
Income(monthly)	Below 10,000 TK	49	17.5	17.5
	10,000-25,000 TK	52	18.6	36.1
	25,000-40,000 TK	41	14.6	50.7
	Above 40,000 TK	138	49.3	100.0
		280	100.0	
Occupation	Student	23	8.2	8.2
	Job-holder	138	49.3	57.5
	Others	119	42.5	100.0
		280	100.0	

Source: Data analysis results

In case of demographic features, the above table 4.1 shows that, in terms of gender, out of 280 respondents, 105 male and 175 female which is 37.5% and 62.5% respectively while in case of age, among 280 respondents, 53 respondent's age is between 15-25 which is 18.9%. 136 respondent's age is between 26-35 which is 48.6%, 53 respondent's age is between 36-45, which is 18.9%. and 38 respondent's age is between 45-55, which is 13.6%. With regard to income, 17.5% (49) of the respondents had a monthly income of below Tk 10000, 18.6% (52) of respondents had a monthly income between Tk 10000-25000, 14.6% (41) of respondents had a monthly income between Tk 25000-40000, and 49.3% (138) of respondents had a monthly income of above Tk 40000. Finally, as per employment status, 8.2% (23) of the respondents were students, 49.3% (138) of respondents were job holders and 42.5% (119) of respondents were included in others like housewife, businessmen etc.

Reliability Analysis

Table-4.2 Reliability Statistics

Constructs	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Price Fairness	.786	03
Ambience	.794	03
Service Quality	.825	04
Food Quality	.780	03
Restaurant Location	.805	03
Customer Satisfaction	.812	04

Source: Data analysis results

The reliability table 4.2 shows that the Cronbach Alpha value for each construct is greater than 0.7, indicating that all of the constructs used in this study, such as price fairness, ambience, service quality, food quality, restaurant location, and customer satisfaction, are internally

consistent, reliable, and valid. If a construct's Cronbach Alpha value is more than 0.60, it is said to be dependable (Ghozali, 2011).

Multiple Regression Analysis

The link between the predictors of customer satisfaction and customer satisfaction was investigated using multiple regression analysis. The values of $R = 0.894$, $R^2 = 0.799$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.796$, and the Standard Error of the Estimate = 0.676 were shown in the following model summary table 4.3. The value of R^2 (0.799) indicated that five independent factors, such as pricing justice, ambience, service quality, meal quality, restaurant location, and so on, explained 79.9% of the variance in consumer satisfaction. This also meant that there was a statistically significant link between predictors and customer happiness.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.894 ^a	.799	.796	.67696

a. Predictors: (Constant), Price_fairness, Ambience, Service_quality, Food_quality, Restaurant_location

Source: Data analysis results

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	500.399	5	100.080	218.382	.000 ^b
	Residual	125.569	274	.458		
	Total	625.968	279			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer_Satisfaction
b. Predictors: (Constant) Price_fairness, Ambience, Service_quality, Food_quality, Restaurant_location

Source: Data analysis results

Anova table 4.4 shows that the given model is significant at 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). And that is the regression model which the researcher tried to fit on the given dataset to establish the relationship between the independent (price fairness, ambience, service quality, food quality, restaurant location) variables and the dependent variable (customer satisfaction).

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.534	.198		2.702	.007
	Price_fairness	.213	.065	.209	3.288	.001
	Ambiance	.344	.064	.339	5.409	.000
	Service_quality	.224	.070	.218	3.216	.001
	Food_quality	.231	.061	.228	3.796	.000
	Restaurant_location	-.172	.076	-.078	-2.264	.024

a. Dependent Variable: Customer_Satisfaction

Source: Data analysis results

The higher the beta, the more significant the factor of customer satisfaction at fast-food restaurants in Kishoreganj, as shown in Table 4.3. It also shows the standardized and unstandardized values (B) for each independent variable, as well as the t-test results and p-values. The T-statistic results were all significant at P less than 0.05. As a result, the model took into account all independent variables. In other words, these characteristics can help explain why consumer satisfaction has changed. Therefore, the table confirmed the result that Ambience was the most important factor affecting customer satisfaction, carried the beta of

0.344 ($P= 0.00$). While, food quality was the second factor affecting customer satisfaction with the beta of 0.231 ($P= 0.00$). The third factor is Service quality having beta of .224 and p value=.001. The fourth factor is Price fairness having beta of 0.213 ($P=0.001$). The only non-accepted factor is Restaurant location factor which is also significant but affect customer satisfaction negatively, having beta -0.172($P=0.024$). So all the hypotheses from H1 to H4 can be supported except hypothesis, H5 related to Restaurant location. Price fairness with beta 0.213 indicates one unit of Price fairness level changes increase customer satisfaction in restaurant sector 21.3% and Ambience having beta of 0.344 expresses when it increased by one unit, customer satisfaction will increase 34.4%.If Service quality having beta of .224 increases one unit, customer satisfaction in restaurant sector will increase 22.4% and one unit increase in food quality with beta .231, customer satisfaction in restaurant sector will be increased by 23.1%. Lastly, restaurant location with beta - 0.172 proves that it is negatively related to customer satisfaction because beta coefficient shows a negative sign but study hypothesis was it is positively related which is true from the theoretical perspective. Hence, finally it is proved that other than restaurant location, price fairness, ambience, service quality, and food quality are positively associated with customer satisfaction. Therefore, H1, H2, H3, and H4 are supported and H5 is not accepted in this research. Thus, these are the significant findings and managerial implications expected to assist to offer more amenable, affordable, valuable, and desirable restaurant services in Kishoreganj, Bangladesh.

Conclusion, Recommendations, Limitations and Future Research Implications

Conclusion

This research aimed to investigate the association of influential determinant with customer satisfaction and explore the most influential factor at fast food restaurants in kishoreganj, Bangladesh. The findings of this research enrich the literature related to food service arena and provide meaningful insights to fast food restaurant industry. In this study, price fairness, ambience, service quality, food quality were found to have positive relationship with customer satisfaction. This research support the findings of prior studies in fast food restaurants (Lefrid, 2021; Richardson et al., 2019; Chun & Nyam-Ochir, 2020; Saneva & Chortoseva, 2020; Zhong & Moon, 2020; Singh et al., 2021b; McNeil & Young et al., 2019; Slack et al., 2020). As a consequence, this research confirmed that all predictors other than restaurant location have positive influence on customer satisfaction and ambience is the best determinant of customer satisfaction at fast food restaurant in kishoreganj, Bangladesh.

Recommendations

In light of research findings, following recommendations are outlined for future research to enhance the existing restaurant service quality and create better customer satisfaction. Firstly, the core focus should be on ambience which denotes the atmosphere of restaurant. So, Restaurants should ensure proper lighting, peaceful music, adequate parking, spacious and clean dining, aesthetically appealing attractive interior and exterior design that comprises an excellent atmosphere within its premises for enhancing the level of customer's satisfaction. Secondly, food quality and culinary experience should be enriched. So, Restaurants should deliver fresh foods on time precisely as per provided food menu to increase satisfaction level. Thirdly, service quality of restaurant must be maintained by fulfilling customer's customized needs through standard, professional, and well-behavior of staffs to enhance customers' level of satisfaction. Fourthly, some expediting factors should be maintained like prompt services, right and desired temperature of the foods, and a neat and gentle appearance of the servers which additionally improve customers' satisfaction. Lastly, managers should establish the price

fairness on their offered foods because Price is a major determinants of customer satisfaction and should not be charged unnecessarily high.

Limitations and Future Research Implications

However, this research is not beyond its limitations. First of all, it is limited to small sample size and is not conclusive research in nature. Therefore, a more rigorous research might be conducted in future where more samples would be surveyed, and more time and money would be invested. In this case, this study creates the scope for investigating a further interest in similar field. Future research can be adopted to examine the existing offerings and practices of restaurants in Kishoreganj. Secondly, the study conducted survey over online, denoting the customers might not have real-time experience at fast food restaurants while fulfilling the questionnaires. Hence, it made the customers to remember their experience and there is a possibility that the customers could not recall the experience properly. Future research should conduct the survey just after respondent leave a restaurant to enhance this research. **Finally**, this research is conducted only in perspective of Kishoreganj. In future, this sort of research should be conducted whole Bangladeshi perspective. To achieve more reliable and precise results, a similar study considering other factors like loyalty, communication, WOM, empathy, commitment etc that influence customer satisfaction in fast food restaurants could be added as variables.

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